

PRIMARY PREVENTION OF ALLERGIC DISEASES

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Abstract. The first manifestation of allergy in young children is most often atopic dermatitis [5]. In the practice of pediatric dermatologists and pediatricians, atopic dermatitis is diagnosed in 1/3 of outpatients [2]. Starting at an early age, atopic dermatitis in children quickly becomes chronic. Children with atopic dermatitis suffer from such manifestations of the disease as multiple scratching, itching and skin inflammation, which are the cardinal symptoms of this disease [8]. The family stress associated with caring for a child with moderate atopic dermatitis significantly exceeds the stress caused by caring for a child with type 1 diabetes mellitus [2]. In addition, the material damage from this disease is significant, since the treatment of atopic dermatitis is a serious financial problem for the family and healthcare in general [4].

In most patients, the disease can persist throughout life [9]. Data on complete clinical recovery from atopic dermatitis vary and range from 17 to 30% [9].

Atopic dermatitis is the first clinical manifestation of the "allergic march" and a significant risk factor for the development of allergic rhinitis and bronchial asthma in children [4]. Approximately 40% of children with atopic dermatitis develop bronchial asthma by the age of 3:4 years [3]. Moreover, such children often have a more severe course of bronchial asthma than patients suffering from asthma alone [2]. An increase in the number of patients with combined allergic pathology is a feature of the coming century [6].

Most researchers predict a further increase in allergies, which dictates the search for new ways to solve the problem, in particular, the introduction of modern prevention methods [1]. Primary prevention, designed to prevent the development of allergies, is the most effective, while secondary or tertiary prevention are aimed at alleviating the severity of the disease or reducing the risk of complications of existing allergic diseases [2]. Since the immune system begins to develop in utero, sensitization is possible even during pregnancy, and preventive measures should be taken already during this period [3]. Numerous studies show that when a pregnant woman's body is exposed to allergens, the fetus activates T-cell immunity along the Th2 pathway [1]. This contributes to an earlier manifestation of the atopic immune response in the newborn, especially in those with a genetic predisposition to the development of atopic diseases [5]. Therefore, timely diagnosis and monitoring of allergic pathology in a woman are necessary to improve the course of pregnancy and minimize the risk of developing allergic diseases in the child [6].

The aim of the study was to examine the health status of young children with a history of intrauterine sensitization and to develop an effective regimen for primary allergy prevention in children.

Research objectives

1. To study the health status, allergy status, and level of "overt" and "latent" sensitization of pregnant women living in Perm and the Perm region, and to modernize the algorithm for their examination.

2. To determine the frequency of development of allergic pathology and the health status of children from women with “overt” and “latent” sensitization.

3. To study the characteristics of clinical manifestations of allergies and the level of sensitization in the study groups of children.

Study results. A high prevalence of allergic diseases was found among pregnant women in the Perm Krai (12.1-19.7%). Allergodermatoses (59.0%) and allergic rhinitis (53.8%) predominate among allergic pathologies in pregnant women. A high incidence of "hidden" sensitization in pregnant women (54.7%) was also found. In this case, women are unaware of their high-risk status for allergic diseases in their newborns and, therefore, do not take any preventive measures. Markers of "hidden" sensitization include elevated levels of total and specific IgE. A high incidence of atopic dermatitis manifestation in the first year of life has been established in children born to women with both "manifest" and "latent" sensitization (54.7% and 51.2%, respectively). A characteristic feature of the clinical picture of atopic dermatitis in these children is the predominance of hyperemia (56.1%), dry skin (57.9%), and cradle cap (56.1%). Elevated levels of total IgE were detected in 44.7% of children with atopic dermatitis, and specific IgE antibodies were detected in 14.3% of cases. A high incidence of risk group VI was found in children in all groups (in the main group - 215.0%, in the comparison group - 193.9%, in the control group - 180.0%), which requires clarification of the criteria for inclusion of children in this group for the purpose of more careful monitoring and implementation of appropriate preventive measures. The proposed initial regimen for primary prevention of allergic pathology in children yields insufficient clinical and immunological results. However, atopic dermatitis is diagnosed less frequently in the study group (50.0% versus 68.2% in the control group), diffuse skin lesions and severe allergic skin reactions are not observed, and there is a tendency toward lower mean eosinophil levels (232.56 ± 51.85 vs. 342.25 ± 69.68 in the control group). Sensitization to the identified allergens is not detected.

Conclusions. The regimen of primary allergy prevention in children using an enterosorbent and a probiotic is highly effective and safe. Children born to mothers who received this regimen of primary prevention of allergic diseases are significantly more likely to have the initial stage of atopic dermatitis (80.0% versus 33.3% in the control group ($p < 0.05$) and 40.0% in the main group), its mild course, and a more favorable morphological picture. In the comparison group, a tendency towards a less frequent occurrence of allergic rashes in the first year of life is noted, atopic dermatitis is diagnosed less frequently (45.5% versus 68.2% in the control group and 50.0% in the main group), a localized allergic process develops more often, and allergic lesions of the mucous membranes are not detected. Conducted antenatal prophylaxis has an impact on immuno-allergological parameters: no sensitization to identified allergens is detected, there is a tendency towards a lower average level of eosinophils and total IgE in children.

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